

Metadata mappings and transformations for PUNCH4NFDI Data Portal

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Abstract

The PUNCH4NFDI consortium [1] brings together representatives from astroparticle, astro, particle, hadron and nuclear physics in order to improve and further develop research data infrastructures in alignment with the special requirements of researchers in these data-intensive research fields. The central element of this vision, the PUNCH Science Data Platform (PUNCH-SDP) [2] is being developed to address needs such as discovery, reuse, and sharing of physicists' research results in digital form, leveraging the resources of federated infrastructures [3].

The central element of the PUNCH-SDP, is the PUNCH4NFDI Data Portal. It provides access to a knowledge fabric connecting the elements of PUNCH4NFDI innovative Digital/Dynamic Research Products (DRP) [2]. This concept abstracts a wide range of digital research outputs, such as data in various states of processing from raw data to fully curated and published data collections, simulations, research papers, software, analysis workflows, etc., supporting data discovery, interoperability and reproducibility of research.

Efficient support for this approach requires the development of a systematic and scalable approach to metadata curation in the system, focusing on operational use of heterogeneous metadata schemas defined in the PUNCH communities, the DRP metadata and broader data curation standards such as those defined in NFDI [4] and EOSC [5].

Our solution involves the development of a multi-level metadata schema that consistently extends the DataCite [6] standard through the DRP level to the discipline-specific metadata standards used in PUNCH communities. Implementing this approach involves the creation of mappings and transformations between each of the schema levels, or provide the means to combine data within clearly defined execution workflows, as well as documenting, standardizing, and assuring quality of metadata records. By

enabling structured and standardized metadata mappings across DRPs, our approach contributes to measurable improvements in data reusability and workflow reproducibility by making it easier to identify compatible datasets, reconstruct processing pipelines, and link research outputs across platforms.

This contribution will highlight recent progress and outline next steps toward implementing metadata mappings and transformations within the PUNCH data portal.

Keywords: Metadata, FAIR data management, PUNCH4NFDI, Physics, Digital/Dynamic Research Product

Resources

1. H. Enke, A. Haungs, T. Schörner-Sadenius et al. Survey of Open Data Concepts Within Fundamental Physics: An Initiative of the PUNCH4NFDI Consortium. *Comput Softw Big Sci* 6, 6 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41781-022-00081-7>. — The publication studies FAIR and open data curation approaches, as well as data models, formats and standards across PUNCH4NFDI research communities (particle, astroparticle, hadron, and nuclear physics);
2. V. Tokareva for PUNCH4NFDI Consortium. Towards coherent metadata schema for the PUNCH4NFDI open science platform. DPG-Frühjahrstagung 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000156245> — The contribution studies discipline-specific metadata standards and practices among PUNCH4NFDI data providers and identifies essential metadata requirements across PUNCH4NFDI communities;
3. Discipline-specific standards in PUNCH4NFDI communities:
 - a) International Lattice Data Grid, Metadata Working Group. <https://www2.ccs.tsukuba.ac.jp/ILDG/> — The resource provides documentation on standardized XML-based metadata schemas for lattice QCD data;
 - b) CERN Open Data portal. CERN Open Data record-v1.0.0. <https://opendata.cern.ch/schema/records/record-v1.0.0.json> — JSON schema, which defines the structured metadata model for high-energy physics datasets;
 - c) International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA) Documents & Standards, <https://ivoa.net/documents/index.html>. — Technical specifications, including discipline-specific metadata standards.
 - d) V. Tokareva. Metadata curation use cases in astroparticle physics. Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration Conference 2022 (HMC Conference 2022). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7157292> — A comparative analysis of metadata curation practices in astroparticle physics;
 - e) I. Knezevic, A.K. Mistry. Developing a FAIR-Compliant Metadata Schema for Experimental Nuclear Physics, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1338689/contributions/6011126/attachments/2951141/5195011/GSI-NAPMIX%20I.Knezevic-%20CHEP%202024.pdf>, 2024. — The contribution covers recent progress in metadata development for curation of digital research objects in experimental nuclear physics and related disciplines;
4. H. Enke, T. Schörner-Sadenius. Science Data Platform and Digital Research Product. *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure* . 1, (Sep. 2023). <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.342>. — The material introduces the concept of Digital Research Product and discusses its value for in-

tegrating heterogeneous data objects and making them accessible through the Science Data Platform;

5. H. Enke, V. Tokareva. (2023). PIDs in the Natural Sciences (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368436> — The material covers data collections and data processing in Astrophysics and in High Energy Physics important for efficient application of PIDs and discusses PID use and the established community procedures in the natural sciences;
6. T. Schörner et al. First Digital Research Products Executed on the PUNCH4NFDI Science Data Platform. 1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI), Karlsruhe, Germany. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8358506> — First PUNCH4NFDI use cases and workflows implemented in the form of digital research products;
7. PUNCH4NFDI Results page: <https://results.punch4nfdi.de/> — Other services, frameworks and publications by PUNCH4NFDI consortium.

Author contributions

All authors contributed to investigation, data curation, conceptualization, and methodology. Individual contributions: H.E. - Supervision, Project Administration; I.K., C.S. - Software; V.T. - Supervision, Writing – original draft; A.H. - Supervision, Project Administration, Writing-Review&Editing; A.K.M. - Supervision, Writing-Review&Editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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- [2] H. Enke and T. Schörner-Sadenius, “Science data platform and digital research product,” in *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, vol. 1, 2023.
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- [4] *Sektion (Meta)daten, Terminologien, Provenienz — NFDI — nfdi.de*, <https://www.nfdi.de/section-metadata/>, [Accessed 09-04-2025].
- [5] M. Gruenpeter, S. Granger, A. Monteil, *et al.*, *D4.4 - guidelines for recommended metadata standard for research software within eosca*, version V1.0 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED

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